
MONTESSORI - AN EFFECTIVE LEARNING APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Maria Montessori's methodology in the development of fine motor skills of children of preschool age should be well studied. The main thing in this technique is that the surrounding people do not hinder the creative energy of an early age. This article analyzes, the different aspects of this educational method, whether it is better or worse than traditional schools, the relationship of the Montessori materials to a child's intellectual, emotional and social development.

Keywords: *Montessori method, education, toddler classes, age groupings, modern-day technology.*

Young children flourish in connections with adults who are secure, supportive, and informed about how to assist their growth and learning. Working with young children from infancy through the early primary years is important and complex, as the science of child development and early learning makes evident. Much has been learned about how children learn and develop as a result of research over the last ten years. Early infancy is a period of development that can have dramatic and long-lasting effects on a child's future, according to studies. The most productive time in a child's development is from birth to six years of age. It is during these years that the baby receives the greatest share of skills and knowledge, which only deepens in later life.

The Montessori method of education is a system of education for children that seeks to develop natural interests and activities rather than use formal teaching methods. The Montessori Method was developed by Dr. Maria Montessori in the early 1900s. It's a specific child-centered method of education that involves child-led activities (referred to as “work”), classrooms with children of varying ages and teachers who encourage independence among their pupils. [Pamela Li] A child has an innate desire to discover and learn about the world, in accordance with Maria Montessori. It is not required to reward or discourage the child in order for him to

teach and educate himself; rather, it is sufficient to "throw a coal" into the furnace of his mind at the appropriate time.

The Montessori Method is a system of child development based on the natural needs, inclinations and abilities of the child. The author of the technique is the Italian pediatrician and teacher Maria Montessori. She based the system on observations of the development of young children with whom she happened to work. Initially, these were babies with various developmental disabilities. Montessori thought through the activities with each child, based on his pace of mastering new skills and age interests. Seeing the success of the system in teaching "special" children, the author adapted the methodology and suggested using it for teaching all young children. Montessori educational education is the basis of preschool and elementary school age education, which was implemented by organizing classes using the environment and didactic materials.

The Montessori system has its own recommendations for each age group. Briefly, the conditional development of a child can be divided into three major stages:

1. From birth to 6 years old - this is the first stage. During this period, the child's personality is formed, and at this age, his main abilities are revealed. This period is unique, and at this time everything is absorbed into the brain. At this time, it is important to correctly understand the information in order to skillfully raise your baby.

2. The second stage - from 6 to 12 years. The main thing in this period is emotional development. The baby is very sensitive and sensitive. These changes are distinguished by their focus. For a long time, the child can focus on things that are more interesting to him without harming other activities.

3. Adolescent age or 12 to 18 years. This is a period of trial and error. Today, the first and most important thing is to get personal experience.

The Montessori model is different from traditional classrooms in many ways. Here are the characteristics of the Montessori learning process:

Mixed-age classrooms. Montessori classrooms are typically arranged by age groups based on three years: infants up to three years old, three to six, six to nine, and nine to twelve. Older students can lead and guide the younger ones when they are struggling. The younger students can benefit from peer learning and moving at their own pace.

Hands on learning. The Montessori classroom environment is highly organized. In a typical classroom, there are shelves full of learning materials, not toys, which

children can freely access to “work” with. They cover a broad range of educational topics and each one supports a specific aspect of child development. These classroom materials are designed in such a way that they can provide corrective feedback. Children can see their mistakes and correct them without a teacher’s close supervision or help.

Freedom of choice. Montessori provides a child-led learning environment. Children can freely choose amongst the displayed working materials. They fall under tightly interconnected curricular areas that encompass sensory, language, mathematics, geography, culture, music, art, and practical life. These activities can help young children learn life skills, feel needed, develop a strong sense of self, and grow a sense of responsibility.

Children's houses generally use interactive, tactile activities to teach topics. For instance, pupils can use sandpaper letters to teach them how to write. These letters were made by cutting sandpaper into letters and mounting them on wooden blocks. The kids then use their fingers to sketch these letters in order to learn each letter's appearance and pronunciation. Another illustration is teaching math concepts, notably multiplication, using bead chains. One bead stands in for one unit, a bar made up of ten beads symbolizes one multiple of 10, a flat shape is made by fusing 10 of the bars together to represent ten, and a cube is made by fusing 10 of the flats together to represent ten times ten. These resources aid in creating a practical understanding of fundamental ideas, which serves as a foundation for much later in life. Montessori schools have mixed-age classrooms, often with 3-year age groupings. There are toddler classes from birth to age 3, primary (or casa) classes for ages 3-6, and elementary classes for ages 6-9 and 9-12. At some elementary schools, all six years are combined into one class. Most middle and high schools have mixed-age classes as well. Parents are encouraged to keep their child in school for at least one full 3-year cycle. [Maria Montessori, 1995]

“Our schools,” says Montessori, “show that children of different ages help one another. The younger ones see what the older ones are doing, and ask for explanations. ... There are many things which no teacher can convey to a child of three, but a child of five can do it with the utmost ease.” (The Absorbent Mind, 1967) [Maria Montessori, 1995: 24]

There is a lot of tangible instructional material that students use. This includes self-correcting crossword puzzles referred to as manipulatives. Additionally, they

work with different materials like beads, tiles, pink towers, sandpaper letters, and blocks.

There are several advantages to concrete learning. These are a few of them:

- Strengthening muscles and improving fine motor abilities are two benefits.
- Children benefit from this connection to reality, which helps them grow up.
- It incorporates movement with learning, engaging a variety of senses in the process.

At least in elementary and primary education, tests and assignments are rarely provided. Middle school students occasionally receive them, but usually for practice. However, they are typically not graded.

Tests and assignments are graded in high school. However, the major purposes of this are to meet Canadian provincial curricula requirements and to get pupils ready for college. Apart from that, grades are not distributed.

Students also don't get much appreciation. When they are, it's for effort rather than results. Since they might undermine motivation and learning, rewards are rarely provided. Students are urged to discover their own incentive instead. Learning becomes its own incentive when students choose their own tasks. This may spark a love of learning that lasts a lifetime. In “The Risks of Rewards” (1994), Alfie Kohn discusses the reward systems. Focusing on reward systems in general, he says:

“Studies over many years have found that behavior modification programs are rarely successful at producing lasting changes in attitudes or even behavior. When the rewards stop, people usually return to the way they acted before the program began. More disturbingly, researchers have recently discovered that children whose parents make frequent use of rewards tend to be less generous than their peers (Fabes et al. 1989; Grusec, 1991; Kohn, 1990).” [Maria Montessori, 2019]

Elizabeth Hainstock, in “*The Essential Montessori*” [Maria, 1994], divides Montessori learning materials into four main groups and, some are used only at certain levels:

- Motor education
- Sensory education
- Language
- Math

Furthermore, community material, modern-day technology, science and culture can be found in more supplemented Montessori schools. Learning is very adaptable. Therefore, advanced students can progress through the curriculum more quickly

while still feeling engaged and challenged. Additionally, it permits struggling students to go more slowly, preventing frustration and disengagement.

Today, there are about 22,000 Montessori schools in the world. Many famous people studied under the Montessori system.

Among them:

- Google founders Larry Page and Sergey Brin;
- Jeffrey Bezos, the founder of the Internet company "Amazon.com";
- Catherine Graham, owner and publisher of "The Washington Post" newspaper;
- There is Gabriel García Márquez, winner of the Nobel Prize in Literature

All in all, contrary to many other alternative educational approaches, Montessori education is becoming more widely used globally and in the public sector. Furthermore, Montessori has hardly evolved since the first part of the 20th century, in contrast to the conventional approach. Because it is a deeply ingrained cultural system that we attempt to enhance by considering as a logical positivist collection of components, even the conventional system has not undergone a significant transformation. Radical transformation might be necessary for true educational reform.

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